

Selection of high-trait emotivity affects the volume of sensory and emotional-related brain regions in male Japanese quails

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Abstract

Japanese quails (*Coturnix japonica*) divergently selected based on their behavior during a tonic immobility test are an excellent model to study the link between brain morphology and behavior expression. The LTI (Long Tonic Immobility) and STI (Short Tonic Immobility) quail lines differ in their level of emotivity, with LTI quails being selected for their high-trait emotivity. Here, comparing the brain regions of the LTI and STI lines of male Japanese quails, we test the hypothesis that this divergent selection could have influenced brain anatomy, in particular, those regions involved in sensory and emotional processing. The heads of twenty, 10 weeks old male Japanese quails (10 STI and 10 LTI) were imaged *ex-vivo* using ultra high-resolution (11.7 Tesla) magnetic resonance imaging. The resulting images were used to create a population-averaged quail brain template and manually segmented 3D whole-brain atlas (openly available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4700522>). The atlas is composed of 191 brain regions, the ventricular system, pineal and pituitary glands. Thanks to this atlas, an exploratory analysis was conducted to compare brain regions between the two lines: the relative volumes of 33 regions were impacted (with 24 larger relative volumes being found in STI).

This demonstrates for the first time in male Japanese quail that genetic selection for a specific emotional behavior (tonic immobility) modifies the anatomy of brain regions involved in sensory and emotional processing.

Keywords

Bird - Brain - Behavior - Coping Style - MRI - Atlas

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Introduction

To understand the biological mechanisms underlying emotion in birds, diverse lines of Japanese quails (*Coturnix japonica*) have been selected based on a variety of behavioral and physiological parameters: Low and High Stress genetic lines were selected for their level of corticosterone in reaction to an unfamiliar environment (Satterlee and Johnson 1988) or STI (Short Tonic Immobility) and LTI (Long Tonic Immobility) lines selected based on their response to a tonic immobility test (Mills and Faure 1991). In line with their behavioral and physiological responses, the STI and LTI lines are recognized to have low and high emotivity, respectively (Jones et al. 1991; Hogg et al. 1994; Richard et al. 2000; Hazard et al. 2005; Faure et al. 2006; Boulay et al. 2013; Bertin et al. 2018). During the tonic immobility test, a quail is held in place on its back inside a U-shaped cradle for ten seconds. Then the time taken for the quail to turn over and stand up is measured (i.e., tonic immobility duration). The LTI line quails display high-trait emotivity during this test by remaining on their back often for the maximum duration of the test (5 min), whereas STI quails often stand up almost immediately (Mills and Faure 1991). During an emergence test, latency is higher for LTI quails than STI (Jones et al. 1991) and LTI quails spend significantly more time in freezing than STI quails during an open-field test (Jones et al. 1991). It has also been shown that these lines have different microbiota, learning abilities and that they use different forms of memory (Lormant et al. 2018; Kraimi et al. 2019). There is also some evidence of the neurobiological mechanisms that could support the difference in emotional behavior between these lines: LTI quails have a higher number of GnIH-related peptide-2 neurons in the median portion of the paraventricular nucleus than STI quails (Poissenot et al. 2019) and they display decreased hippocampal neurogenesis compared to STI quails (Lormant et al. 2020b).

Based on the differences between the LTI and STI lines of quail, we hypothesize that this genetic selection for high-trait emotivity could have more globally influenced the anatomy of brain regions involved in sensory (olfactory, auditory and visual) and emotional processing. In line with this hypothesis, the selection of Red Junglefowl (*Gallus gallus*) based on their divergent levels of fear of humans (tameness) is also known to modify brain anatomy (Agnvall et al. 2017). The Red Junglefowl selected for high-trait tameness had a lower total brain weight. However, the modifications to brain anatomy were also region dependent: high-trait tameness led to a lower relative telencephalon weight but to a higher relative cerebellum weight (Agnvall et al. 2017).

To test our hypothesis, we measured the volume of anatomical regions of the quail brain using ultra high-resolution (11.7 Tesla) magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). To be able to investigate the brain in this way an anatomical atlas is required (for example in humans, Talairach and Tournoux 1988). A

cerebral MRI atlas is a 3D digital space providing a standard system of anatomical coordinates and a segmentation (total or partial), voxel by voxel of the anatomical regions. It can represent a single region (human hypothalamus, Baroncini et al., 2012), a single hemisphere (marmoset, Liu et al. 2018; pig, Saikali et al. 2010), an individual brain (human, Tzourio-Mazoyer et al. 2002) or a population-averaged brain (Van Essen and Dierker 2007; Cabezas et al. 2011; Evans et al. 2012; Love et al. 2016). In birds, several atlases exist, such as for pigeon (Güntürkün et al. 2013), starling (De Groof et al. 2016), zebra finch (Poirier et al. 2008) and canary (Vellema et al. 2011). But, due to the specificities of these birds that could be songbird, migratory etc., it is necessary for the current work to have an atlas and template specific for the Japanese quail. However, for Japanese quail, only a paper-based stereotaxic atlas created from colored brain sections exists (Baylé et al. 1974), which is not optimal for use with MRI. In this context, we created a population-averaged quail brain template and manually segmented it to create an MRI-based quail whole-brain atlas. These tools enabled us to achieve the main aim of this work, which was to compare the brain regions of the LTI and STI lines of Japanese quails.

Materials and methods

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Animal care and experimental treatments complied with the guidelines of the French Ministry of Agriculture for animal experimentation and European regulations on animal experimentation (86/609/EEC). They were performed in accordance with the local animal regulation (authorized C37-175-1) of the French Ministry of Agriculture in accordance with EEC directive and with the ethical committee Val de Loire (agreement N° 1848).

Animals

Twenty 10 weeks old (at sexual maturity) male Japanese quails (*Coturnix japonica*) were included in this work. Half of the quails came from the STI line while the other half came from the LTI line (Mills and Faure 1991); all came from the 65th generation of selection. Male quails were chosen because in females the reproductive cycle and laying are associated with changes in hormones that may interact with brain function and anatomy. Quails were selected and bred at the INRAE poultry experimental facilities (INRAE 1295 Unité Expérimentale Pôle Expérimental Avicole de Tours, F-37380 Nouzilly, France, doi:10.15454/1.5572326250887292E12). On day 21 after hatching, sex was determined by feather dimorphism and males were reared in individual cages in a battery (41 cm × 51 cm × 25 cm) under a 12:12 h light dark schedule (light on 06:00 h). A piece of artificial turf was placed on the cage

floor to allow animals to exhibit dust bathing behavior. Ambient temperature was maintained at approximately 20 ± 2 °C. Food and water were provided *ad libitum*. At 10 weeks of age, each quail was euthanized with an overdose of intravenously injected pentobarbital 6% (36mg/100g) before transcardiac perfusion with 400 mL of ice cold 4% paraformaldehyde solution in 0.1M phosphate buffer for brain fixation. After perfusion, the head was severed and kept in the same fixative solution until MRI acquisition.

MRI acquisition

To prevent interference with the MR signal by the presence of air in the feathers, the quails' heads were plucked. Before acquisition, the heads were rehydrated in phosphate buffer to recover T_2 -signal and maintained in a Falcon tube filled with Fluorinert. *Ex-vivo* structural MRI were acquired using a preclinical Bruker BioSpec 11.7 T MRI scanner at NeuroSpin (Gif-sur-Yvette, France). The MR scanner was equipped with a strong gradient set ($G_{\max}=780$ mT/m, slew-rate=9500 T/m/s) and a 40 mm Bruker ^1H transmit-receive volume coil. Anatomical MR images of the quail heads were realized using a T_2 -weighted 2D spin echo (SE) sequence with the following parameters: isotropic 150 μm voxel resolution, flip angle $\text{FA}=90^\circ$, echo time $\text{TE}=16$ ms, repetition time $\text{TR}=9000$ ms, read bandwidth=65789.5 Hz, 8 averages and 1 repetition, total scan duration of 2h45 min.

Template creation

From the MRI SE images, brain masks were manually drawn using ITK-Snap software (version 3.6, <http://www.itksnap.org>, Yushkevich et al. 2006) to enable 'skull-stripping', before being realigned in the AC-PC plane (anterior commissure – posterior commissure). These 20 brain images were used to create the population-average using the `antsMultivariateTemplateConstruction2.sh` function of the ANTS toolkit (Avants et al. 2008; Avants et al. 2011; Avants and Gee 2004). Briefly, template construction involved:

- 1) Creating an initial target template by averaging the skull-stripped images;
- 2) Pairwise normalization of each skull-stripped image to the target template;
- 3) Create new target template by averaging the normalized images output during step 2;
- 4) Transform the new target template by the average inverse affine transform and the average inverse warp field multiplied by a scaling factor (0.2);
- 5) Iterate steps 2 to 4 four times.

Atlas creation

Segmentation:

The segmentation was manually completed by three experts in neuroanatomy (MS, MM, EC) using the ITK-Snap software. During segmentation contrast level, colormap and zoom level were modified to optimize the delineation of each region. The entire right hemisphere was segmented before the left.

The brain is commonly segmented into telencephalon, diencephalon, etc. according to the embryonic vesicles development in the aim to compare the bird and mammalian brains (Reiner et al. 2004; Jarvis et al. 2013; Puelles et al. 2019). However, in the current work we used a combination of MRI contrast, anatomical landmarks and other sources of neuroanatomy, in particular Puelles et al., 2019, to complete the segmentation (Fig 1). For example, based on MRI contrast and external landmarks, we were able to identify the apical and ventral part of the hyperpallium. Dorsally, the apical hyperpallium appeared as a gray area visible on the sagittal plane. Ventrally, its limit was not easy to identify, especially in its lateral borders. Yet, we could see a thin, weaker contrast layer (about 2 to 4 voxels thick) that forms the ventral hyperpallium. The limit between these two parts was easily visible by the shape of the brain that forms the vallecule. However, we were unable to completely segment some known brain regions using this procedure. Subsequently, some brain nuclei were segmented as a unique region of interest, such as for the parts of mesencephalic substantia nigra or for the accessory oculomotor nuclei (see Table 1 for more details). In addition, based on image contrast we were able to distinguish different subparts of several regions (*e.g.*, hindbrain and optic tectum) but we were unable to individually label these parts based on other sources of neuroanatomy.

Labellisation (Table 1):

We defined the name of segmented regions using the Puelles et al. 2019 atlas of the chick brain as our main reference and sometimes other references for specific regions. For example, in the periaqueductal gray (PAG), there is a distinction between this region based on an anatomical or a neurochemical criterion. In this case, we chose to dissociate two different parts of PAG: the dorsolateral part (neurochemical, Kingsbury et al. 2011) and medioventral part (anatomical, Puelles et al., 2019). Another example concerning the entopallium: this region is clearly visible on the MRI quail brain template. Named entopallium in several previous publications (Butler and Cotterill 2006; Wylie et al. 2009; Xiao and Güntürkün 2018), it is named visual core and shell nuclei by Puelles et al. 2019 in the chick brain atlas. We chose to keep the name entopallium.

Volume comparison

The created template and atlas were used to automatically segment the regions of the atlas in each of the 20 individual brains. The function `antsRegistrationSyN.sh` (Avants et al. 2011; Tustison and Avants

2013) was used to compute a non-linear transformation between each individual's MRI SE image and the template. Using `antsApplyTransforms` this transformation from template to individual was applied to the atlas file - each voxel of an individual brain was thus labelled as a specific region. Each individual atlas-based segmentation was verified and none required obvious manual correction.

For each individual the total brain volume (mm^3) and the volume of each segmented region were calculated (number of voxels in the region multiplied by the volume of a voxel, $(150 \mu\text{m})^3$). To remove the potential confound of intersubject variability of total brain volume the region analysis was conducted on relative region volumes. The relative volume of each region, expressed as a proportion, was calculated by dividing its volume by the individual's total brain volume and multiplying by 100.

All statistical tests were conducted using R software (R Core Team, 2020). To examine the impact of genetic selection of high-trait emotivity, independent sample t-tests (function `t_test` from the `rstatix` package; Kassambara 2020) were used to compare the volume of the whole brain and the relative volumes of interhemispheric regions between STI and LTI lines. For bilateral relative region volumes mixed-effect ANOVA with 2 factors were conducted: Hemisphere (right/left) as a within factor and Line (STI/LTI) as a between factor. ANOVA and t-test assumptions were checked using Shapiro-Wilk normality test (function `shapiro_test` from the `rstatix` package) and Levene's test for homogeneity of variance (function `levene_test` from the `rstatix` package). Eighteen regions did not meet the normality assumption and 6 did not meet the homogeneity of variance assumption. For these regions we subjectively investigated the data. Statistical tests were conducted only for regions meeting the assumptions. Statistical significance was assessed at $p < 0.05$. As this work is exploratory we chose to not correct for multiple comparisons that would require to divide the significance threshold by the number of brain regions.

Results

Template and atlas presentation

In this work a population-averaged MRI template of the male Japanese quail brain (Fig 2), an accompanying manually segmented digital atlas (Fig 3) and a nomenclature were successfully created. They are openly available for download (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4700522>) under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. The template and atlas images are provided in compressed NIfTI-1 format (`nii.gz`). A Look-Up-Table (LUT) containing the correspondence between a region's nomenclature, segmentation label, RGB color and transparency value (100% for left

hemisphere and interhemispheric, and 65% for right hemisphere) is also provided in the format required by the ITK-Snap software. The template and the atlas are in the same space, oriented in the AC-PC plane. The X axis corresponds to the left to right anatomical axis, the Y axis corresponds to the posterior to anterior axis and the Z axis corresponds to the inferior to superior axis.

The success and quality of the template creation procedure can be seen when compared to individual quail brain images. The template produced displays less noise, increased contrast between gray and white matter and enhanced delineation of anatomical regions compared to individuals (Fig 2). The atlas contains the greatest number of regions of interest that we were capable of segmenting using the image contrast and anatomical landmarks of the template. In this context, the MRI atlas of the male Japanese quail brain comprises 194 segmented regions of interest. It includes 191 brain regions (9 interhemispheric, 91 left and 91 right hemisphere), the ventricular system and the pineal and pituitary glands (Fig 3). In Table 1 these regions were classified following three different types of organization: according to the embryonic vesicles, according to the mammalian brain (neurolex.org) and according to the chick brain atlas (Puelles et al. 2019). Furthermore, for certain regions Table 1 includes details of, for example, the nomenclature for the region used in other publications and/or the nomenclature of regions that could not be segmented individually but were instead incorporated within a larger segmented region of interest.

Global view

Mean brain volume of STI ($925 \pm 62.2 \text{ mm}^3$) and LTI ($917.1 \pm 63.2 \text{ mm}^3$) quails were not statistically different ($t=-0.56$, $p=0.58$). The importance of analyzing the volume of each region relative to total brain volume was confirmed by the large variability of total brain volume in each group (range: STI, $852.5 - 1006 \text{ mm}^3$; LTI, $781.6 - 984.3 \text{ mm}^3$; Table 2).

Concerning the region volumes, the statistical assumptions were tested for 100 brain regions (91 bilateral and 9 interhemispheric regions), the pineal and pituitary glands. The statistical assumptions were not met for 22 bilateral and 2 interhemispheric regions. No further statistical analyses were conducted for these regions. The effects of line, hemisphere and their interaction were tested on 69 bilateral regions and the effect of line was tested on 7 interhemispheric regions and the pineal and pituitary glands.

For 9 regions, we found a significant interaction between line and hemisphere (see Table 3, 4 and 5 for all statistical details and Supplementary file 1). For 33 regions, we found a significant difference between STI and LTI quails, with larger relative volumes mainly being found in STI (24/33 regions)

rather than in LTI (9/33 regions). For 53 regions, we found a significant difference between the left and right hemispheres, with larger relative volumes in the left hemisphere for 31 of them.

Regions involved in sensory processing (see Table 3)

Olfactory:

There was no significant difference between the lines for the relative volume of the olfactory bulb, which was significantly larger in the right than in the left hemisphere. In contrast, there was a significant interaction between lines and hemispheres for the olfactory tract. Its relative volume was larger for STI than for LTI quails and this difference was larger in the left hemisphere than in the right.

Auditory:

The relative volume of the midbrain vocal area and the dorsal nucleus of the lateral lemniscus were significantly smaller in LTI than in STI and larger in the left than in the right hemisphere. Subjective observation of the data also indicates a larger relative volume of the olivary cochlear area in LTI than in STI.

Visual:

For optic tectum (Fig 4), mesencephalic reticular formation and isthmus nucleus, there were significant interactions between lines and hemispheres. For each, relative volume was smaller in LTI than STI with this difference being larger in the right than the left hemisphere. Similarly, LTI presented smaller relative volumes than STI for rotundus nucleus (Fig 4), periventricular and central stratum, dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, ventral hyperpallium and for tectopretectal, tectotegmental and isthmotectal tracts. Moreover, subjective observations of the tectal gray and tectotegmental decussation indicated the same effect. In contrast, the opposite effect (LTI larger than STI) was found for the relative volume of the entopallium (Fig 4). The relative volume of the rotundus nucleus, tectopretectal tract, optic tract and oculomotor nerve were significantly larger in the right than in the left hemisphere. In contrast, the relative volume of entopallium, periventricular and central stratum, ventral hyperpallium and tectotegmental, isthmotectal and isthmooptic tracts were significantly larger in the left than the right hemisphere. Subjective observation of the data indicates a larger relative volume of tectal gray and tectotegmental decussation in the left than in the right hemisphere.

Moreover, the relative volume of the mesopallium, which is involved in both auditory and visual processing, was smaller in LTI than in STI and the right hemisphere was larger than the left.

Regions involved in emotional processing (see Table 4)

For amygdala-related regions, the relative volumes of extended amygdala, frontoamygdaloid and amygdalohypothalamic tracts were significantly larger in the left than the right hemisphere. Moreover, subjective observation of the data indicates a larger relative volume of the anterior amygdala area in LTI than STI in both left and right hemispheres and a larger relative volume in the right than in the left hemisphere. Subjective observation of the data also indicates that the relative volume of arcopallium-amygdaloid complex was smaller in the left than in the right hemisphere. However, in the right hemisphere, LTI was larger than STI whereas there was no difference between lines in the left hemisphere. For amygdaloid taenial area, subjective observation of the data indicates that the relative volume was larger in LTI than in STI only in the right hemisphere.

For the bed nucleus of stria terminalis and the substantia nigra, there were significant interactions between lines and hemispheres. The relative volume of the bed nucleus of stria terminalis was significantly larger for LTI than STI but only in the right hemisphere. The relative volume of the substantia nigra was smaller in LTI than STI in both hemispheres with the difference being larger in the right than the left hemisphere.

For thalamus, dorsolateral and dorsomedial anterior thalamic nuclei, there were significant differences between the lines. For each, relative volumes were smaller in LTI than STI. However, the relative volume of thalamus and dorsomedial anterior thalamic nucleus were significantly larger in the left than in the right hemisphere whereas the relative volume of dorsolateral anterior thalamic nucleus was smaller in the left than in the right hemisphere. Moreover, the relative volume of the lateral striatum was significantly larger in LTI than in STI whereas the relative volume of lateral hypothalamus was significantly smaller in LTI than in STI.

For septum, caudocentral septal area, hypothalamus, hippocampus (Fig 4), accessory oculomotor nuclei, there were significant differences between the hemispheres. The relative volume of septum, hypothalamus and accessory oculomotor nuclei were significantly larger in the left than in the right hemisphere. In contrast, the relative volume of caudocentral septal area and hippocampus were significantly smaller in the left than in the right hemisphere.

Subjective observation of the data indicates that the relative volumes of the dorsal (Fig 4) and medio ventral parts of the periaqueductal gray were smaller in LTI than in STI. However, the relative volume of the dorsal part of the periaqueductal gray was smaller in the left than in the right hemisphere whereas the relative volume of the medio-ventral part of the periaqueductal gray was larger in the left

than in the right hemisphere. Subjective observation of the data also indicates that the relative volume of the accumbens nucleus was smaller in LTI than in STI and smaller in the left than in the right hemisphere.

For the cerebellum, there were significant interactions between lines and hemispheres. The relative volume of lobule 1 was larger in LTI than STI only for the right hemisphere. For lobule 9 and cerebellum white matter, the relative volumes were significantly larger in LTI than STI in both hemispheres with the difference being larger in the left than in right hemisphere. The relative volumes of lobules 2, 3, 4 (Fig 4) and 5 were significantly larger in LTI than in STI. Moreover, the relative volumes of lobules 3, 5, 7, 8, 9 and cerebellar peduncle were significantly larger in the left than the right hemisphere whereas the relative volume of lobule 4 was significantly smaller in the left than the right hemisphere.

For the endocrine glands (pineal and pituitary), a significant difference was found for the pineal gland, which was smaller in LTI than STI.

Regions involved in other processing (see Table 5)

The relative volumes of midbrain, preoptic area and preisthmic region of the midbrain were significantly smaller in LTI than in STI. Moreover, for preisthmic region of the midbrain, the relative volume was larger in the left than in the right hemisphere. The relative volumes of apical hyperpallium, nidopallium and ambiguous nucleus were larger in the right than in the left hemisphere. On the contrary, the relative volumes of anterior pretectal and subpretectal nuclei, striatopallidal area, semilunar nucleus, ventral tegmental area and caudal hindbrain were smaller in the right than in the left hemisphere.

Discussion

In line with our hypothesis, we demonstrated for the first time in male Japanese quail that genetic selection for a specific emotional behavior (tonic immobility) is able to modify the anatomy of brain regions involved in sensory and emotional processing. These results are in agreement with previously published data in the Red Junglefowl (Agnvall et al. 2017) indicating that genetic selection can modify brain anatomy. The differences in relative volumes observed in our study may be due to several microstructural modifications (Asan et al. 2021). For example, in the grey matter, it may be due to a change in the number or size of the different cells. In the white matter, it may be due to a difference in

the number or size of the fibers or even the myelin composition. Moreover these differences may be associated with modification of specific neurotransmitter systems described in the quail brain (*e.g.*, neuropeptide Y, Boswell et al. 1998; serotonin, Cozzi et al. 1991; calcitonin gene related peptide, Lanuza et al. 2000).

The examination of sensory-related regions (in particular olfactory, visual and auditory) demonstrated that several were affected by genetic selection of high-trait emotivity. This suggests that the divergent selection impacted globally the sensory abilities of quails. In visual-related regions, the rotundus nucleus was impacted. Its lesion has also previously been shown to induce an attenuation of red color-preference in quail artificially color-imprinted (Csillag et al. 1995) suggesting the importance of the rotundus nucleus in color and visual perception. These observations suggest that visual perception contributes to the difference in emotivity between STI and LTI lines. These results also provide some support for the speculation that LTI quails display different sensory processing of environmental cues than STI quails (Calandreau et al. 2013). It is important to further assess and compare the perceptual abilities of STI and LTI lines to fully understand the link between perceptual ability, brain anatomy and genetic selection of high-trait emotivity.

The examination of emotional processing regions highlighted numerous differences throughout the emotional neuronal network. The relative volume of arcopallium-amygdaloïd complex and other amygdala-related regions were smaller in STI than LTI quails, further confirming the role of these regions in emotivity. The implication of the arcopallium in the quail emotional neuronal network was previously demonstrated by the lesioning of arcopallium in LTI, which reduced their fear level (Saint-Dizier et al. 2009). Moreover, subjective observation of the data for the PAG showed an impact of divergent selection on the relative volume of this region. These results highlight the involvement of PAG in emotivity in quails (Takeuchi et al. 1996). The PAG is known to be involved in coping style (Bandler and Shipley 1994; Zelena et al. 2018) thus the difference in emotional reaction during the tonic immobility test between the STI and LTI may reflect a more general difference in their coping style. The relative volume of several cerebellar lobules were also impacted, suggesting that the cerebellum may be involved in emotion in birds as has been shown in mammals (Adamaszek et al. 2017; Moreno-Rius 2018). Divergent selection (high or low reproductive investment) has already been shown to modify purkinje cell size and foliation in the cerebellum of Japanese quails (EL-Andari et al. 2020). The relative volume of the hippocampus was smaller in the left than in the right hemisphere whereas there was no difference between STI and LTI quails. We had expected a difference for the relative volume of the hippocampus between STI and LTI because it is involved in spatial memory (Lormant et al. 2020a) and LTI preferentially use spatial memory whereas STI preferentially use

cue-based memory (Lormant et al. 2018). However, this difference in the form of memory used could be explained by a difference in sensory perception. As suggested above, STI and LTI quails may perceive their environment differently, which implies an adaptation of the forms of memory used.

Despite a difference in the corticotropic axis between the two quail lines (Hazard et al. 2005), we did not find any significant difference in their pituitary volumes. In contrast, pineal gland volume was smaller for LTI than STI. It is possible to speculate that this difference is associated with differences in melatonin synthesis and secretion (Gómez Brunet et al. 2002). As melatonin is involved in the stress response in neonatal chicks it would be interesting to investigate the putative role of melatonin in the emotional reactivity of the LTI and STI quails (Saito et al. 2005).

Genetic selection of high-trait emotivity also affects regions involved in other physiological processes. For example, the relative volume of the preoptic area was significantly smaller in LTI than in STI quails. The preoptic area is involved in sexual behavior, in particular because of the presence of aromatase (Balthazart and Foidart 1993; Absil et al. 2001). Based on these results, it would be interesting to compare the sexual behavior of male STI and LTI quails to test whether the difference of relative volume leads to a modification of this behavior.

It is well known that the brains of many birds are functionally and structurally lateralized (Manns and Ströckens 2014; Güntürkün and Ocklenburg 2017) but, to our knowledge, no studies have investigated either the functional or structural lateralization of the Japanese quail brain. However, quails do display behavioral lateralization in a visual task (Valenti et al. 2003). The current results highlighted several brain regions differing in relative volume between the left and right hemispheres regardless of the line. Future work could investigate whether these anatomical differences also reflect a functional lateralization of the Japanese quail brain (Moorman and Nicol 2015; Güntürkün and Ocklenburg 2017).

The current work was conducted with sexually mature male quails. Future work could investigate the developmental trajectory of the differences in brain morphology between these quail lines; do they exist *in ovo*, at birth or during early maturation? To our knowledge, the developmental trajectory of total or regional quail brain volume is unknown. Based on the developmental trajectory of the zebra finch (*Taeniopygia guttata*) brain, we can speculate that at 10 weeks of age the quail brain has already reached its maximum volume (Hamaide et al. 2018). Furthermore, it would be important to investigate whether or not the same differences in brain morphology also occur for female LTI and STI quails.

Such work would also enable the creation of a template and atlas comprised of both male and female quails, which would be optimal for studies explicitly investigating the factor sex.

Conclusion

This exploratory work shows for the first time in Japanese quail that genetic selection for a specific emotional behavior (tonic immobility) is correlated with widespread modification in brain anatomy. Here we mainly focused on how this selection influenced the anatomy of several sensory and emotional processing brain regions. The widespread modification also suggests that the connectivity of brain networks would differ between the LTI and STI quails; a hypothesis that we are currently investigating using diffusion-weighted imaging. The exploratory approach taken here facilitates the creation of more focused hypotheses relating changes in brain structure to differences in expressed behaviors or cognitive capacities.

Illustrations

Table 1 List of the brain regions labeled in the quail brain atlas, according to the embryonic vesicles, the mammalian brain (neurolex.org) and the chick brain atlas (Puelles et al. 2019). Each bilateral brain region is numbered in the Look-Up-Table (LUT) according to the left (1-100) and the right (101-199) hemisphere, except the mammillary bodies segmented as a unique region (label 48). Specific LUT-values are used for interhemispheric tracts (401- 408), endocrine glands (601, 602) and ventricular system (701)

Table 2 Individual total brain mask volumes (mm^3) for Short (STI) and Long (LTI) Tonic Immobility quails. The total volume includes the pituitary and pineal glands volumes

Table 3 Relative volumes (mean % \pm standard error) of brain regions involved in sensory processing according to the hemisphere (Left-H, left hemisphere; Right-H, right hemisphere). Statistical values in bold indicate a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) of the tested factors (line, hemisphere and interaction for bilateral regions; line for interhemispheric regions). The highest significant values observed for line are underlined, for hemisphere are bold. For the regions with no statistical analysis, the # indicates that the assumption of normality was not met and the ## indicates that the assumption of equality of variance was not met

Table 4 Relative volumes (mean % \pm standard error) of brain regions involved in emotional processing according to the hemisphere (Left-H, left hemisphere; Right-H, right hemisphere). Statistical values in bold indicate a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) of the tested factors (line, hemisphere and interaction for bilateral regions; line for interhemispheric regions). The highest significant values observed for line are underlined, for hemisphere are bold. For the regions with no statistical analysis, the # indicates that the assumption of normality was not met and the ## indicates that the assumption of equality of variance was not met

Table 5 Relative volumes (mean % \pm standard error) of other brain regions according to the hemisphere (Left-H, left hemisphere; Right-H, right hemisphere). Statistical values in bold indicate a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) of the tested factors (line, hemisphere and interaction for bilateral regions; line for interhemispheric regions). The highest significant values observed for line are underlined, for hemisphere are bold. For the regions with no statistical analysis, the # indicates that the assumption of normality was not met and the ## indicates that the assumption of equality of variance was not met

Fig. 1 Pictures of the different steps of segmentation. First brain regions were identified in the template (top and middle) and were then segmented (bottom) according to sagittal (left) and coronal (right) sections of the template. Image contrast was used for most of the regions such as entopallium (1), lateral striatum (2), amygdaloid complex (3), optic tectum (4) and periventricular and central stratum (5). In other cases, image contrast and external landmarks were used to identify the border of brain regions such as the apical (6) and ventral (7) hyperpallium, which are separated by the vallicula (arrow). (A, anterior; P, posterior; R, right; L, left)

Fig. 2 Template (top) and two individual quail brain (middle, STI quail 7427 and bottom, LTI quail 7133) pictures of coronal (left), sagittal (middle) and axial (right) sections of the male Japanese quail

Fig. 3 Pictures of the manually segmented Japanese quail atlas, represented in the three spatial views: axial (top left), coronal (top right), sagittal (bottom right) and in 3D view (bottom left)

Fig. 4 Impact of high-trait emotivity selection on relative volumes (% of total brain volume) of brain regions involved in sensory (optic tectum, rotundus nucleus, entopallium) and emotional (hippocampus, dorsolateral part of the periaqueductal gray, lobule 4 of the cerebellum) processing. Individual (small dots), mean (large dots) and standard error values (error bars) are represented in grey for LTI and in black for STI quails, according to the left and right hemispheres. Note the lack of

statistical values for the dorsolateral part of the periaqueductal gray that did not meet the statistical assumptions. (R, right; L, left; A, anterior; P, posterior)

Declarations

Funding and Competing Interest

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Author Contributions

EC, LC, BM, FA, CP contributed to the study conception. EC, LC designed the final study. RYH, JB and DAB performed the MRI acquisition. SAL and MS created the MRI template. MS, MM and EC manually segmented MRI atlas. MS, SAL and EC performed data analysis and interpretation. MS, SAL and EC wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors critically revised the manuscript and approved the final version.

Availability of data and code

The template, atlas and LUT are openly available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4700522>. The anatomical MRI (.nii.gz format) for each of the 20 quails, their individual atlas-based segmentations (.nii.gz format), the region volume data (.csv format) and R code (.Rmd and .html format) used for statistical analysis will be available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5584517>) when this manuscript has been accepted for publication.

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